

THE FEATURES OF TRANSLATING BUSINESS LETTERS

Babamuradova Nozima Farkhod kizi

Master's student Uzbek state world languages university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7982879>

Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of translation and methods of translation of official business documents, as well as the style of business documents. The study of translation methods is of great interest both from a linguistic and cultural point of view.*

Keywords: *business correspondence, business translation, formal business style, translation, conciseness, clarity, literacy, design standard.*

The main feature of the language of business correspondence is an accurate and clear presentation of the material with an almost complete absence of emotional elements. They practically exclude the possibility of arbitrary interpretation of the essence of the issue. Therefore, the main requirements that a good business translation must meet are: accuracy - all provisions interpreted in the original must be stated in the translation;

conciseness - all provisions of the original are concisely and concisely presented in translation;

clarity - brevity and conciseness of the target language should not affect the completeness of the transmission of the original vocabulary;

Literary - the text of the translation must meet the generally accepted norms of the literary language, without the use of syntactic structures of the original language. In Russian, more formal forms of signing a business letter are used. The phrase "Respectfully yours (name)" is usually used.

The link consists of two parts: the initials of the one who dictates the letter, and the initials of the secretary, or the one who types the letter, so that the culprit of any errors can be quickly identified. In Britain, the link is most often located under the date, and in America - in the lower left corner.

The application is on the left after the link. A postscript is added to inform the recipient of a particularly important point, but it should not contain new information that was not previously mentioned: PS. PS: PS- P.S.

For example: P.S. If you order within 10 days, I am authorized to offer a 10% discount.

If the content of the letter does not fit on one page, then each subsequent page must have a title sheet continued (name of the addressee, date and page number).

In addition, one of the most important points that a translator needs to know when translating a letter from English is that a very polite form of communication is adopted in business letters in English. For example: If you will be able to come, we will invite you for an interview at 9 a.m. In Russian, these forms of communication are more formal: Please arrive at 9:00 for an interview. Also, the functional style of official business literature (FSOBL) is more inclined to use words of Romance origin, which are more formal, than native English, which are less formal.

Formal business style is the most conservative style in any language, so deviation from the norms in writing or paperwork will be perceived as impolite, and sometimes even an insult. Therefore, the translator in this type of text should be especially careful not to hurt the feelings and dignity of the Receptors, and not to violate official business etiquette. In addition, it is

important to add that structural forms are preserved in business correspondence and certain syntactic constructions are used, which is the main feature that characterizes business correspondence. So, any official letter has the following parts: heading, date, introductory address, body text, final courtesy formula and signature. These blocks are regulated both at the lexical and syntactic level. Thus, the translation of business documentation also has its own characteristics - it is, first of all, following strict rules and using certain, standardized clichés.

For all business letters, there is a certain design standard that is important to strictly observe, since the appearance of the letter forms the first impression of the person who received it. The following are the main elements of a business letter and the rules for their design:

1. Envelope. According to the unified standard for the design of envelopes, information is located in a strictly defined place and order. The following is a general scheme for the design of an English envelope. • Sender's First Name, Last Name, - Brand, Apartment/House Number, Shipping Method Name Street Name, City, State/Area, Zip Code, Country • Recipient's First Name, Last Name, Apartment/House Number, Street, City, State/Area, postal code, country.

2. Name and address. This element in most cases is printed at the top of the page (letterhead), which is used, as a rule, only for the first page of the letter.

3. Date. It is written five lines after paragraph 1.

4. Address of the recipient. It is filled in the same way as on the envelope.

5. Specific addressee. In the case when the letter is sent to the address of the company, but addressed to a specific person, "ATTENTION" and the name of the recipient are written in capital letters.

6. Appeal. Try to always address by name, you can also use the title and position of the recipient.

7. The subject of the letter. This position is optional, but its presence once again shows a polite attitude towards the addressee. The recipient of the letter can immediately understand whether it is necessary to give the letter immediate attention, as the topic concludes how important it is. The subject line can be underlined or written in capital letters.

8. Text of the letter. It is recommended to highlight paragraphs of text not with indents, but with intervals.

9. Formal completion of the letter. In order to end a letter politely and at the same time formally, you can use these standard forms, as: "Yours truly", "Sincerely yours", "Respectfully yours".

10. Company name of the sender. In less formal correspondence, this element is quite often omitted. The name should be put in the event that the author of the letter writes not on his own behalf, but on behalf of the whole company.

11. The name of the writer, his position and rank. Printed four lines after the preceding paragraph to leave space for the signature.

12. Initials of the author and executor of the letter. The initials of the author should be written in capital letters, then after a colon or a fraction, already in small letters - the initials of the person who typed the letter.

13. List of applications. If there are attachments, then you need to write the word "Enclosure" and make a list of the attached files. This ensures that important documents that are attached to the application are viewed.

In the event that a copy of this letter is sent to another addressee, the sign “cc” must be put at the end and the name of the recipient of the copy of the letter. Punctuation in the translation of business documents deserves special attention. They allow you to build the structure of a phrase when writing, dividing it into logical groups, which facilitates an accurate and clear understanding of the meaning.

REFERENCES

1. ВАНСЛАВ, М. В., ЯРВ, И. В., & ИВЛЕВА, Е. С. (2013, April). Особенности перевода деловых писем и контрактов. In *Филология и лингвистика: проблемы и перспективы: материалы II междунар. науч. конф.*(г. Челябинск (pp. 96-98).
2. Котий, Г. А., &Гюльмисаров, В. Р. (1999). *Деловые письма на английском языке. Образцы с переводом на русский язык: практ. пособ./ГА Котий, ВР Гюльмиссаров.–М, 1.*
3. Аполлова, М. А. *Specific English: Грамматические трудности перевода. Международные отношения. – 1977.*
Гуринович, В. В. (2005). *Деловая переписка на английском языке. М.: АСТ, Харвест.*
4. Аизова, А. М. *Основы деловой переписки. – 1996*